

MECHANICAL PROPERTIES OF HTPB PROPELLANT STRIP BIAXIAL TENSION SPECIMEN

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ABSTRACT

To investigate the mechanical properties and fracture mechanisms of hydroxyl-terminated polybutadiene (HTPB) propellant at low temperature and high strain rate, biaxial tensile tests were conducted over the range of temperatures 223 to 298K and strain rates 0.4 to 42.86s⁻¹ using an INSTRON testing machine, and scanning electron microscope (SEM) was employed to observe the tensile fracture surfaces. The experimental results indicate that the deformation properties of HTPB propellant are remarkably influenced by temperature and strain rate. The characteristics of stress-strain curves at low temperatures are different from that at room temperature, and the effects of temperature and strain rate on the mechanical properties are closely related to the changes of properties and the fracture mechanisms of HTPB propellant. With the decrease of temperature and the increase of strain rate, the stress value gradually increases. The biaxial mechanical properties for HTPB propellant under biaxial stretching are not only influenced by the micro-damage of the propellant, but also affected by the molecular structure of the propellant itself.

1 INTRODUCTION

Solid rocket motor (SRM) has become the main power plant and the core components of strategic and tactical missile weapon system^[1]. The solid propellant grain is the main power source of SRM, so the analysis of solid propellant grain structural integrity becomes more important. Propellant is a kind of viscoelastic material whose mechanical properties are affected by ambient temperature and loading strain rate. To ensure the normal operation of solid rocket motor, it is necessary to study the mechanical properties of solid propellant at low temperature and high strain rate^[2-3].

At present, the mechanical properties of solid propellant under uniaxial tension condition at low temperature and high strain rate and the condition which is low temperature and low strain rate by biaxial tension are studied by researchers at home and abroad^[4-8]. The mechanical properties of the propellant under biaxial tension at low temperature and high strain rate are still scarce. D'Andrea et al.^[9] proposed the stress state of the inner hole surface of the solid propellant grains can be approximated as the biaxial tension state. Therefore, it is very important to study the mechanical properties of solid propellant under biaxial tensile stress.

The mechanical properties of the solid propellant under biaxial tensile stress can be studied only by the uniaxial tensile testing machine due to the characteristics of the structure of the propellant strip. Therefore, the mechanical behavior of HTPB propellant under low temperature dynamic biaxial stretching is studied by using a new type of high-strain-rate hydraulic servo test machine and strip test piece, and the dynamic characteristics of biaxial tension curve are analyzed.

2 EXPERIMENTAL

The material used in this investigation was taken from the composite rocket propellant and consists of an 88 wt % mixture of ammonium perchlorate (AP) and fine aluminum particles bound together with 12 wt % of a HTPB polymer binder. The solid propellant biaxial strips were tested at temperatures of 223, 243, and 298 K and at strain rates of 0.40, 4.00, 14.29 and 42.86s⁻¹.

In this investigation, the tensile tests were conducted on a classical testing machine INSTRON VHS 160/100-20, which can guarantee the strain rate up to 20 m/s at temperature interval from -113 K

to 973 K and can apply optional thermal loading conditions to the testing sample with a thermal chamber. The samples were stored at the test temperature for an hour prior to testing and were then tested at a strain rate until they fractured shown in Fig.1. Five replicates were run at each test conditions and all stress–strain curves investigated in the following sections were the average of the five data sets. A Quanta 600FEG SEM was used for routine post-failure examination. Samples were mounted using a conductive paint onto SEM stubs and sputter coated with a thin layer of gold prior to examination.

Fig.1 The classical testing machine and the combination of physical map

3 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

3.1 Stress-Strain Behavior

The stress-strain curves of HTPB propellant at various test conditions are shown in Figure 2 which use the normalized data and the characteristics are represented as follows:

1.The curve characteristics of the propellant were consistent with the uniaxial tension studied by Wang et al.^[10].Firstly, the stress-strain curve of the propellant still exhibits a strong nonlinearity with the increase of strain, and the influence of temperature and strain rate is obvious. With the decrease of temperature and the increase of strain rate, the stress value gradually increases.On the other hand, the stress-strain curves of the propellant still exhibit typical characteristics of the elastic, damage and failure stages at room temperature or lower strain rate. The stress-strain curve of the propellant also exhibits a "bimodal phenomenon" which was shown by uniaxial tension at -30°C and high strain rate, and the stress of the propellant is still reached at a low strain under -50°C and high strain rate , and then decreased rapidly.

2.Compared with the uniaxial tensile test results, the non-linear section of the stress-strain curve of the propellant is more steep and the decrease of elongation is more obvious in the biaxial stretching.

Fig.2 Stress-strain curves of the biaxial tensile test for HTPB propellant at various temperatures and strain rates (a) 298 K; (b) 243 K; (c) 223 K.

3.2 Mechanical Properties

The initial modulus E_{bt} , maximum tensile strength σ_{bmt} and maximum elongation ϵ_{bmt} of the HTPB propellant in the tensile direction of the testing machine during biaxial stretching were determined directly from the curve shown in Fig.3.

The curves of the typical mechanical properties of the HTPB propellant in the tensile direction of the tester during biaxial stretching at different temperature and strain rate are shown in Fig.3. In order to more clearly describe the mechanical properties of HTPB propellant under dynamic biaxial stretching, the logarithmic scale factor of the initial modulus and the maximum tensile strength are taken in Fig.3.

Fig.3 Mechanical parameters of HTPB propellant (a) The initial modulus;(b) The maximum tensile strength;(c) The maximum elongation.

The initial modulus and maximum tensile strength of the HTPB propellant in the tensile direction of the tester under biaxial stretching increase with increasing the temperature and strain rate and follow the linear double logarithmic relationship with the strain rate shown in Fig.3. And the maximum elongation also increases with the temperature, but the relationship with the strain rate is complicated. At room temperature, the maximum elongation increases first and then decreases with the increase of strain rate, and reaches the maximum at strain rate of 14.29s⁻¹. At low temperature, the maximum elongation decreases with the increase of strain rate, and the effect of strain rate changing on the maximum elongation becomes more obvious with the decrease of temperature. When the temperature decreases to -50°C, the effect of strain rate changing on the maximum elongation at high strain rate becomes very weak. Under the combined effect of low temperature and high strain rate, the maximum elongation at -50°C and 42.86s⁻¹ is about 18.2% of the value at 25°C and 14.29s⁻¹.

The effects of temperature(25,-30 and -50°C) and strain rate(0.40,4.00,14.29 and 42.86s⁻¹) on the mechanical properties of HTPB propellant were analyzed by two-factor analysis of variance. The values obtained by analysis of variance when taking the significant level of 0.05 shown in Table.1, and F_{crit} is the critical value.

Influencing factors	The value of initial modulus	The value of maximum tensile strength	The value of the maximum elongation	F_{crit}
Temperature	44.0171	119.4907	11.8411	5.1432
Strain rate	11.9197	35.9633	0.3111	4.7571

Table 1. Analysis of variance of biaxial tensile mechanical properties of HTPB propellant

The values of the biaxial tensile mechanical properties of the HTPB propellant are much higher than F_{crit} of the HTPB propellant for temperature, but only the values of the initial modulus and maximum tensile strength is greater than F_{crit} for the strain rate shown in Table 1. The results show that the temperature influences the mechanical properties of the HTPB propellant, and the strain rate has a significant effect only on the initial modulus and the maximum tensile strength, which is different from the uniaxial tension. In addition, the temperature values corresponding to the mechanical properties are greater than the strain rate, which indicates that the mechanical properties of the HTPB propellant under biaxial stretching are more susceptible to temperature, which is consistent with the uniaxial stretching. The temperature and strain rate values corresponding to the maximum tensile strength are larger than the values corresponding to the initial modulus and the maximum elongation, indicating that changes in temperature and strain rate under biaxial stretching are more likely to cause the significant changes of the maximum tensile strength of HTPB propellants.

3.3 Damage Mechanism

In order to analyze the change of mechanical properties of HTPB propellant at low temperature and high strain rate under biaxial stretching and reveal the effect of stress state on the mechanical properties of propellant, the SEM of HTPB propellant under biaxial tension condition is shown in Fig.4.

The meso-damage mode of the propellant is still mainly the interfacial damage ("dehumidification") and the matrix tearing between the AP particle and the matrix at low temperature and low strain rate. With the increase of the strain rate, the degree of "dehumidification" reduce. When the strain rate continues to rise, the microstructures of the propellant become AP particle breakage, and the critical strain rate of the damage form from the "dehumidification" and matrix tearing to AP particle fracture is in the range of $14.29 \sim 42.86\text{s}^{-1}$. At low temperature, the meso-damage mode of the propellant is mainly AP fracture, and the damage degree increases with the increasing of the strain rate.

Fig.4 SEM images of the tensile fracture surfaces for HTPB propellant at various temperatures and strain rates ($\times 200$) (a) 298 K and 0.40s^{-1} ; (b) 298 K and 14.29s^{-1} ; (c) 298 K and 42.86s^{-1} ; (d) 223 K and 0.40s^{-1} ; (e) 223 K and 14.29s^{-1} .

With the decrease of temperature and the increase of strain rate, solid propellant becomes hard and brittle, and the damage degree of mesostructure increases. Therefore, the effect of horizontal stress on microcrack propagation in propellant is weakened gradually. It is the main reasons why the maximum

elongation of the propellant is basically not affected by the stress state at low temperature and high strain rate. In addition, the macromolecular chains in the solid propellant are constrained by the two directions at the same time, so that it is no longer easy to cause the sliding deformation between molecular chains in one direction. The tensile strength of the propellant is much higher than that of the uniaxial tension, and the maximum elongation of the propellant is lower than that of the uniaxial tension.

4 CONCLUSIONS

According to the behavior of HTPB propellant at low temperature and high strain rate under biaxial tensile, the deformation and meso - damage of the propellant were obtained under the temperature range of $-50 \sim 25^{\circ}\text{C}$ and the strain rate range of $0.40 \sim 42.86\text{s}^{-1}$. Based on the experimental results, the stress-strain curves, the mechanical properties and the meso-damage of the HTPB propellant under low temperature dynamic biaxial stretching were analyzed. The effects of temperature, strain rate and multi-axial stress state on the propellant mechanical properties and meso-damage of the HTPB propellant and the intrinsic relationship between the macro-mechanical properties and the meso-damage of the HTPB propellant were obtained. The main conclusions are following:

The temperature and strain rate can significantly affect the biaxial tensile mechanical properties of HTPB propellant under biaxial stretching conditions. The stress-strain curves of the propellant under biaxial stretching are basically the same as those of uniaxial tension. The change of the typical mechanical properties of the propellant with temperature and strain rate is also consistent with the uniaxial tension. The results show that the effect of temperature and strain rate on the typical mechanical properties of HTPB propellant under biaxial tension is basically the same as that under uniaxial tension. The main difference is that the maximum elongation of the propellant is less affected by the strain rate under biaxial tension.

The initial modulus and maximum tensile strength of the HTPB propellant can be improved by biaxial tensile loading, but the maximum elongation of the propellant is significantly reduced, that is, the propellants are more likely to fail due to reduction of elongation under biaxial stretching conditions. Therefore, the maximum elongation of the propellant under biaxial stretching conditions can be selected as the failure criterion for structural integrity analysis of solid propellant grains under ignition and pressure build-up conditions. In addition, the maximum elongation of the HTPB propellant under biaxial stretching conditions is no longer affected by the stress state and is approximately constant with the continuous decrease of temperature and the increasing strain rate.

The biaxial loading can reduce the damage of the propellant especially at room temperature or lower strain rate. This is mainly due to the fact that the stress in the horizontal direction does not affect the direction of microcrack formation and propagation in the propellant, but it will affect the propagation speed of microcracks. In addition, the maximum tensile strength and maximum elongation of HTPB propellant under biaxial stretching are not only influenced by the micro-damage of the propellant, but also affected by the molecular structure of the propellant itself.

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